

Black Titanium Oxide/Activated TaS₂ Flakes Photoelectrode for Plasmon Assisted Hydrogen Evolution at Neutral pH at High Current Density

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A heterojunction photo-electrode(s) consisting of porous black titanium oxide (bTiO₂) and electrochemically self-activated TaS₂ flakes is proposed and utilized for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The self-activated TaS₂ flakes provide abundant catalytic sites for HER and the porous bTiO₂, prepared by electrochemical anodization and subsequent reduction serves as an efficient light absorber, providing electrons for HER. Additionally, Au nanostructures are introduced between bTiO₂ and TaS₂ to facilitate the charge transfer and plasmon-triggering ability of the structure created. After structure optimization, high HER catalytic activity at acidic pH and excellent HER activity at neutral pH are achieved at high current densities. In particular, with the utilization of bTiO₂@TaS₂ photoelectrode (neutral electrolyte, sunlight illumination) current densities of 250 and 500 mA cm⁻² are achieved at overpotentials of 433, and 689 mV, respectively, both exceeding the “benchmark” Pt. The addition of gold nanostructures further reduces the overpotential to 360 and 543 mV at 250 and 500 mA cm⁻², respectively. The stability of the prepared electrodes is investigated and found to be satisfying within 24 h of performance at high current densities. The proposed system offers an excellent potential alternative to Pt for the development of green hydrogen production on an industrial scale.

efficiency in sunlight energy utilization.^[2-4] Among various approaches to overcome these drawbacks one of the simplest, even though very efficient way, is the formation of so-called black titanium – self-doped Ti³⁺ increasing the number of oxygen vacancies, surface disordering, and/or surface hydrogen doping.^[5-8] In the structure of black titanium, the Ti³⁺ sites ensure an additional energy level in the band gap, resulting in more efficient visible light absorption and simultaneously acting as redox-active centers.^[9-13] Contradictionally, the Ti³⁺ centers can act as charge recombination sites, decreasing the overall materials' photoelectrochemical efficiency.^[14] This problem can be eliminated by coupling black titanium (or other photoactive material) with redox-active materials, which scheme enables charge carriers to be drawn and subsequently participate in water splitting.^[6,15-19] Such a heterojunction-based strategy which can be achieved by coupling black titania with noble-metal-free semiconductor(s) is especially attractive for application purposes.^[20-26]

The coupling of TiO₂ with another semiconductor, such as carbon nitride, metal oxides, and sulfides (especially MoS₂) has been reported to significantly enhance photochemical or photoelectrochemical hydrogen production.^[23-30] Even this question is actually being considered as an important background for ensuring a safe future economy based on “green energy”.^[31,32] Main

1. Introduction

One of the most frequently used materials for photoelectrochemical water splitting and green hydrogen production, known from 1972, is titanium oxide (TiO₂).^[1] However, TiO₂ has a wide band gap and relatively fast charge recombination rate, which limits its

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Figure 1. Schematic representation of the sample preparation: anodization of Ti foil for formation of TiO_2 nanotube array, reduction of TiO_2 and creation of black titanium oxide (bTiO_2), deposition of Au layer and its disruption for creation of Au nanoclusters, deposition of TaS_2 flakes and their final electrochemical self-activation.

attention has been focused on the effect of illumination on hydrogen production in terms of observed photocurrent or solar-to-hydrogen efficiency.^[23,24,27–30] However, the potential of such materials in hydrogen production at high current densities and in photo-electrochemical mode, remains almost unexplored. At the same time, the development of rare-metal-free materials for hydrogen production at “close to the industrial” scale represents one of the most urgent scientific challenges.^[33,34] In this light, the paper of D. Guo et al, published in 2022, represents one of the rare attempts to discover the potential of Ti oxide (stoichiometric TiO_2 was used) coupled with metal sulfides for hydrogen production at high current densities (i.e., close to commercially acceptable 500 mA cm^{-2}) and with efficiency comparable to those based on platinum.^[35]

In this work, we propose coupling nanotubular black TiO_2 (bTiO_2) with electrochemically self-activated 2D TaS_2 as a catalyst in photoelectrochemical hydrogen production. We also tested the addition of plasmon-active gold nanostructures between used semiconductors, which could ensure surface plasmon excitation, enhance light absorption, and facilitate charge excitation/separation.^[36–40] Unlike previous reports, our main attention is focused on the utilization of the created electrode's hetero-junction for hydrogen production at high current density and neutral pH. Our results on material efficiency and stability are compared with the “benchmark” Pt catalyst.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Main Experimental Concept of Heterojunction Photoelectrode Preparation

The schematic representation of the experimental route for the creation of $\text{bTiO}_2@\text{Au}@\text{TaS}_2$ (or $\text{bTiO}_2@\text{TaS}_2$) heterojunction photoelectrode is given in **Figure 1**. We started from the 1D TiO_2 nanotube array, created by electrochemical anodization of the initial Ti foil (anodization parameters were optimized regarding the final structure morphology and catalytic activity – see SI for details, including complete characterization/conformation of Ti anodization and TiO_2 reduction, Figures S1–S6, Supporting Information). Such a nanotube array provides a large specific surface area, maximizes the surface area between the electrolyte and electrode surface, and ensures multiple photons scattering on the surface. Further, the created titanium oxide was electrochemically reduced to form bTiO_2 with a corresponding surface disorder of oxygen vacancies to enhance light absorption. For this goal, we used the well-established experimental route.^[5] In the next step, the Au layer was deposited on the samples' surface and then disrupted by plasma treatment. In this way, a plasmon-active array of Au nanostructures (nanoclusters) was created. Subsequently, the separately prepared TaS_2 flakes were deposited on the sample surface using an

electrophoresis procedure (the samples are subsequently referred to as $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$).^[41,42] Detailed characterization of TaS_2 flakes is given in SI (Figures S7–S10, Supporting Information). An alternative set of samples without the intermediate Au layer was created by direct deposition of TaS_2 flakes on the bTiO_2 mesoporous surface (the samples are referred to as $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@TaS}_2$). In both cases, samples at the final step were subjected to electrochemical self-activation, performed in an H-type electrochemical cell with a separation membrane (to avoid the Pt deposition from the counter electrode). As was reported previously, electrochemical self-activation leads to flake cracking and/or formation of vacancies on the basal planes, which is accompanied by a significant increase in catalytic activity.^[41,43] Finally, we evaluated the photoelectrochemical activity toward the hydrogen evolution reaction, with a particular emphasis on the functionality of the samples at high current densities and neutral pH.

2.2. Particular Materials and Final Samples Characterization

The porous structure of as-anodized Ti (i.e., formed TiO_2 nanotube morphology) is presented in Figure S1 (Supporting Information). After optimization, the sample with 140 nm pore size was selected, taking into account the typical size of activated TaS_2 flakes, which were expected to penetrate the surface pores (and additional optimization tests are presented in Figure S6, Supporting Information). Formation of the bTiO_2 layer after electrochemical reduction of porous TiO_2 was evident as black staining of the samples (Figure S5, Supporting Information) and additionally confirmed by X-ray diffraction, measurements, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XRD, XPS), and Raman spectroscopy. In the XRD pattern (Figure S2, Supporting Information), the larger linewidth of the characteristic peaks, their slight shift to higher diffraction angles as well as the appearance of several new reflexes indicate the creation of a surface disordered layer, oxygen vacancies, and reduction of the interplanar distance of the titanium crystalline phase.^[44,45] Shift of the Raman vibration bands (Figure S3, Supporting Information), also confirms the formation of the bTiO_2 layer and the presence of oxygen vacancies in the bTiO_2 structure.^[6,46] Finally, XPS spectra indicate the titanium oxidation after the 1st step of substrate preparation (anodization) and its partial reduction with the formation of oxygen vacancies and surface disordering after the bTiO_2 layer formation (Figure S4, Supporting Information).^[47–49]

In turn, the survey XPS spectra of TaS_2 (Figure S9, Supporting Information) show that the tantalum oxide was successfully converted to TaS_2 . The production of even the 3R- TaS_2 phase was confirmed by XRD measurement (3R phase, ref. 01-077-3359 – Figure S7, Supporting Information). Raman spectroscopy reveals the presence of 390 and 290 cm^{-1} vibration bands, corresponding to the A_{1g} and E_{2g}^1 vibrational modes of 3R- TaS_2 phases (Figure S8, Supporting Information).^[50] Finally, the 2D structure of as prepared 3R- TaS_2 flakes was confirmed by atomic force microscopy measurements (Figure S10, Supporting Information).

After the deposition of TaS_2 flakes on the surface of bTiO_2 or $\text{bTiO}_2\text{@Au}$ we observed the inhomogeneous distribution of relatively large flakes (Figures S11 and S12, Supporting Information). However, subsequent TaS_2 self-activation (the final step in

Figure 1) significantly modifies the photoelectrode's surface morphology, the changes being visible in field-emission electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images (Figure 2A,B; Figures S13 and S14, Supporting Information). In both cases the flakes were cracked and “smeared” across the whole bTiO_2 or $\text{bTiO}_2\text{@Au}$ surface, the presence of larger flakes was not observed. Corresponding energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) maps of Ta and S distribution indicate the closed to homogeneous covering of the photoelectrode surface by TaS_2 (Figure S14, Supporting Information). Comparison of survey XPS spectra measured before and after activation, indicates some loss of TaS_2 during the activation (due to flakes breaking). This phenomenon is also confirmed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) measurements (Table S1, Supporting Information). Preparation of TiO_2 nanotube array as well as deposition and treatment of Au and TiS_2 on bTiO_2 were also accompanied by changes (increase) in surface area (determined as nitrogen sorption desorption on a 1×1 cm sample surface – Table S2, Supporting Information). Finally, Au penetration inside TiO_2 pores was confirmed by cross-section SEM-EDX images (Figures S15 and S16, Supporting Information). In turn, part of Au remains on the surface of the sample.

The optical properties of created photoelectrodes were also characterized by measurements in light reflection mode with the utilization of an optical probe with high numeric aperture (Figure 2C). As is evident from the spectrum of anodized TiO_2 , the light absorption decreases significantly with increasing light wavelength(s). The “missing” light at shorter wavelengths can be attributed to both intrinsic absorption by TiO_2 and light scattering on the roughed surface (which is evident from the apparent “white” color of the surface – Figure S5, Supporting Information). In turn, TiO_2 reduction results in the increase of light absorption, especially pronounced at longer wavelengths (in this case the light absorption is evident even from apparent samples blackening). The deposition of Au and TaS_2 (or solely TaS_2) with subsequent photoelectrode self-activation led to a further increase of light absorption, especially pronounced near infrared (NIR) wavelengths (Figure 2C). The detail of the ultraviolet-visible (UV–vis) spectrum of plasma-treated $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au}$ sample, presented in Figure S17 (Supporting Information), shows the presence of a plasmon absorption band. Additional Raman measurements of crystal violet also indicated the apparent enhancement of the Raman response of this dye, confirming the presence of plasmon-related surface enhancement of Raman scattering (SERS– Figure S18, Supporting Information). In summary, the prepared photoelectrode can efficiently absorb the entire sunlight spectrum, from near to UV up to NIR wavelengths.

2.3. Electrochemical Self-Activation and Photoelectrochemical Tests of Samples Functionality – Acidic Electrolyte Case

Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves, probing HER activity in acidic electrolytes after various periods of electrochemical self-activation for $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@TaS}_2$ and $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$ electrodes are presented in Figure 3A,B. As is evident, the LSV curves shift toward lower overpotential in both cases. Moreover, in both cases shapes of the curves are close to the Pt standard, indicating great hydrogen production ability.

Figure 2. A,B) FE-SEM images of bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂, C) UV-vis absorption spectra, measured in the reflection mode at various stages of sample preparation.

The significant impact of the intermediate Au layer is observable too – for bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ self-activation proceeds significantly faster, compared to the case of bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂. Even after a “short” activation time (3 h) the shape of LSV curves becomes close to the benchmark (Pt electrode). In general, the electrochemical activity of the Au-containing samples (bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂) is higher than that of those without Au. This is evident also from measured overpotentials for a current density of 10, 25, and 50 mA cm⁻² – 0.080, 0.116, and 0.157 V (vs RHE) for bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂, in comparison to 0.095, 0.128, and 0.175 V, required for self-activated bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂. Thus, from the obtained results it can be concluded that TaS₂ flakes cracking resulted in a significant increase of catalytic activity due to the increased number of edges and probably, additional vacancies formed. The process is significantly accelerated by the introduction of an intermediate Au layer, which is expected to facilitate the charge transfer between bTiO₂ and TaS₂ and related enhancement of both activation kinetic and final material redox activity.^[51] Additionally measured XRD patterns and XPS spectra (Figures S19–S21 and Table S3, Supporting Information) indi-

cate the conservation of TaS₂ crystalline and chemical structure (from high-resolution XPS graphs the appearance of some sulfur vacancies during activation is also evident as a shift of characteristic sulfur and tantalum related peaks). In addition, a shift in the XPS peaks of Ta and S was observed after activation, which can be attributed to the charge redistribution between TaS₂ and b-TiO₂ due to the improvement in the coupling of these semiconductors (Figure S20, Supporting Information). Such an improved coupling can support better charge separation and enhance the overall material(s) catalytic activity.

It should be also noted that from the calculated Tafel slope(s), the dramatic increase in catalytic activity after TaS₂ self-activation can be attributed to the changes in the HER rate-determining step (Figure S22, Supporting Information). Before the activation, the HER seems to be limited by the Volmer step (Tafel slope is close to 100 mV dec⁻¹), indicating the adsorption of hydrogen cations as a limited stage. However, after activation, the Tafel slope was measured to be 53 mV dec⁻¹, which corresponds to the characteristic Heyrovsky mechanism, determined by the kinetic of hydrogen molecule associative desorption. In the next step,

Figure 3. A,B) LSV curves (dark case) measured at HER potentials in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 electrolyte with utilization of $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@TaS}_2$ and $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$ electrodes during electrochemical self-activation, Pt is given as electrode benchmark; C,D) electrochemical samples response to light illumination, measurements were performed in LSV mode at HER potentials, insets reflect chronoamperometry at -0.18 V versus RHE with simulated illumination on and off; E,F) EIS curves obtained on $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@TaS}_2$ and $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$ electrodes in dark or under simulated sunlight illumination.

the expected light-induced enhancement of the catalytic activity was examined in photo-electrochemical measurements. First, the impact of simulated sunlight illumination as well as illumination at separated wavelengths is illustrated in Figure 3C,D for $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@TaS}_2$ and $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$ photoelectrodes. As is evident, HER performance is enhanced in both cases, under illumination in the case of $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$, where the impact of plasmon triggering catalytic activity and Au-mediated photo-excited charge transfer is evident. Even better HER performance was observed with the utilization of simulated sunlight illumination. In this case, the overpotentials at 10, 25, and 50 mA cm^{-2} current densities were shifted up to 0.051, 0.090, and 0.131 V

for $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$ and up to 0.067, 0.106, and 0.144 V for $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@TaS}_2$ (vs RHE). The cycles of light switching ON/OFF are shown as inserts in Figure 3C,D. For both types of samples, we observed the immediate response to illumination, indicating the contribution from photo-excited charges to HER kinetic. In addition, for $\text{bTiO}_2\text{NTs@Au@TaS}_2$ a gradual increase of current was observed, which can be attributed to plasmon heating, due to a slower response. In this case, the electrode surface as well as the closed electrolyte layer can be gradually heated under plasmon-assisted light-to-heat conversion, enhancing in this way HER kinetic.

We also performed a range of wavelength-dependent experiments (Figure S23, Supporting Information). Obtained results

indicate that the samples “positively” respond to the typical wavelength of the sunlight spectrum, but the more pronounced response (i.e., a noticeable photocurrent density increase) was observed with the utilization of wavelengths close to the absorption band of bTiO₂ or to plasmon resonance excitation.

The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) curves, measured in the dark or under illumination, are presented in Figure 3E,F. The charge transfer resistance, evident as semicircles radii on EIS spectra, between the sample surface and the electrolyte (dark mode) was found to be smaller in the case of bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂, also indicating the positive impact of Au intermediate layer. Illumination of the samples results in a significant decrease in charge transfer resistance, which is consistent with previous LSV results. Based on the overall electrochemical characterization at HER potentials, it can be concluded that the created photoelectrode shows significant photo-response under a wide spectrum of light illumination, which is evident as an improvement of charge transfer and HER performance too. The results obtained with bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ (photo)electrode overperform the alternative electrode without plasmon-active metal addition.

To further highlight the role of activated TaS₂, we also performed control experiments with the utilization of Au@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au electrodes (Figure S24, Supporting Information). Au@TaS₂ was prepared by Au sputtering on a Ti sheet with subsequent electrophoretic deposition of TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au was prepared in accordance with the procedure explained in the experimental part. Subsequent measurements reveal low HER activity, which otherwise could be expected. In addition, photoelectrochemical experiments reveal that both systems are positively affected by illumination, however, the shift of LSV curves was insufficient to achieve HER activity comparable to bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ or bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ surfaces.

To perform hydrogen efficiency evaluation, we compared our electrodes (bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂) with the benchmark Pt electrode and followed the hydrogen evolution by the mass spectrometer. When setting -10 mA on platinum and on the sample of interest, we recorded on a mass spectrometer a change in the signal with mass 2 (m/z2, corresponding to H₂). It can be seen from Figure S25 (Supporting Information) that the intensity of hydrogen evolution on the sample at a given current is comparable to the hydrogen evolution on the Pt surface. Thus, we can conclude that the activated electrode produces hydrogen with Faradic efficiency comparable to that of the benchmark Pt (the experiments were performed in the dark).

2.4. Neutral pH Electrolyte and High Current Density Tests

Considering the modern trends in water splitting, oriented toward maximum simplification of raw material sources, minimization of additional agents, and the use of natural resources (water), our further efforts were focused on hydrogen production under neutral pH. So, previously activated samples were used and sunlight energy was utilized as additional energy input. Furthermore, our experiments were primarily directed toward achieving high current water splitting, which could be practically appealing and technically feasible. Figure 4A,B shows LSV curves, measured up to relatively large current

densities (500 mA cm⁻²). The Pt electrode curves, a commonly used “benchmark” for hydrogen production, are also included for comparison. In both cases, bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂, the location of the LSV curves was found to be close to the Pt standard. Moreover, the efficiency of HER on the bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ photoelectrode surface overperforms that on the bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ surface. For better clarity, the overpotentials measured at current densities of 10, 100, 250, and 500 mA cm⁻² are presented in Figure 4C,D. As is evident, both bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ heteroelectrodes show slightly worse catalytic activity compared to Pt standard at a current density below 100 mA cm⁻². However, simulated sunlight illumination partially compensates for this drawback and shifts required overpotentials toward the characteristic Pt value(s). The better results obtained with the utilization of bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ heteroelectrodes highlight the contribution of Au nanostructures to HER efficiency in the photoelectrochemical regime. The phenomenon can be attributed to the better charge transfer between bTiO₂NTs and TaS₂ thanks to intermediate Au nanostructures.

In turn, LSV curves measured on our samples and Pt control intersect with increasing potential, and starting from certain current densities, the higher catalytic activity of bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ samples in comparison with that of Pt were observed. The sunlight irradiation also has a positive effect at high current densities, especially pronounced in the bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ case. This trend is further supported by the overpotential values, which are comparable to Pt in the dark for bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and surpass Pt in the case of photoelectrochemical experiments. Even more promising outcomes were achieved with the sample containing an additional Au layer. In particular, the bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ samples require even less voltage to achieve a current density of 500 mA cm⁻² than the Pt control electrode or bTiO₂NT@TaS₂ electrode. In this instance, the impact of light illumination and plasmonic initiation of catalytic activity is also evident, leading to a notable reduction in overpotential during measurements under illumination compared to the dark mode.

We also investigated the effect of the TaS₂ loading amount on the photoelectrode performance (hydrogen evolution). A series of activation processes for different electrophoretic deposition times were conducted. From the obtained results (Figure S26, Supporting Information), it is evident that the shortest deposition time (lowest loading) results in a worse overpotential but steeper curve slope. For higher loading times (300 and 600 s), the overpotential for hydrogen evolution decreased. However, with increased loading, we obtained a smaller curve slope. In this case, the steeper LSV slope corresponds to a larger electrochemically active surface and better coverage of TaS₂ on the electrode surface.

2.5. Stability Tests at High Current Densities in Neutral pH

In the next step, the stability tests in a photoelectrochemical mode at neutral pH under various current densities were performed. In this regard, it should be noted that the stability of photoelectrodes based on bTiO₂, as well as the heterojunction electrodes derived from it, is sometimes regarded as a

Figure 4. A,B) LSV curves measured up to high current densities in neutral pH with utilization of bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ photo-electrodes, measurements were performed in dark mode and under illumination with simulated sunlight, Pt standard is also added for comparison; C,D) estimated from LSV curves the values of overpotentials required to reach different current densities (up to 500 mA·cm⁻²) in the dark or under illumination of bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ photo-electrodes.

questionable one. This is attributed to the diffusion of surface vacancies into the material's bulk, leading to a weakening of redox activity and interphase charge transfer.^[5,52] The results obtained in our case are presented in **Figure 5A,B**. As is evident, 24 h of performance at the current density of 100 mA cm⁻² does not affect the catalytic activity toward HER for both bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ photo-electrodes. Stability tests performed at high current densities indicate some worsening of catalytic activity after a certain time. However, the decrease of the catalytic activity is not significant and the increase of potential required for 500 mA cm⁻² does not exceed a few percent. Moreover, the electrode morphology and materials crystallinity remain also unchanged, which is evident from SEM-EDX (Figure 5C,D vs, Figure 2) as well as from Raman measurements (Figure S27, Supporting Information) measurements, performed after the stability tests. Noteworthy, the stability performance at high current densities highlights the attractiveness of the proposed hetero-junction photoelectrode for “close-to-industrial” scale hydrogen production from “raw” water with neutral pH.

To estimate the composition of the electrolyte after stability tests, we performed several ICP-MS measurements (Table S1, Supporting Information). As is evident, Pt can dissolve (from the counter electrode surface), but cannot reach the working electrode surface, since we used a separated H-type electrochemical cell. However, we observed apparent amounts of Ta near the working electrode surface, which indicates that this material is gradually removed. Thus, some decrease

in bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ HER activity can be expected with time. On the other hand, this potential problem can be solved by further optimization of the TaS₂ flakes deposition route.

We also compare our results with previously published ones (Table 1). In this case, the main attention was focused on HER efficiency, which has been reached with the utilization of various hetero-junction-based nanostructures. As is evident, the proposed bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ electrode has an efficiency comparable to the best-published ones in terms of overpotentials to achieve “low” current density. The bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ electrode shows even greater efficiency, which exceeds most previously published ones (especially in the photo-electrochemical mode).^[53–61] At the same time, it is worth noting that the number of works aimed at using hetero-structures in the high-current HER mode is limited. In this sense, our results can be considered very useful and attractive for further, practically oriented development of cheap but effective structures for water splitting.

2.6. Results Summarization and Proposed Mechanism

The proposed photoelectrode's design (with subsequent activation) allows their utilization with relatively high current densities even at neutral pH. Moreover, the created structures overperform Pt at high current densities. In addition, simultaneous electrode surface illumination and utilization of sunlight as

Figure 5. A,B) Stability tests, performed at neutral pH (photoelectrochemical mode) and at different current densities with utilization of bTiO₂NTs@TaS₂ and bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ photo-electrodes; C,D) samples' surface characterization after the stability tests (500 mA cm⁻² current density, 24 h); E) proposed mechanism of plasmon-assisted charge transfer excitation and participation in HER (solely better bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ case is presented), residual holes are consumed in second water splitting half-reaction – oxygen evolution).

Table 1. Comparison of our results with previously published ones (HER with utilization of coupled semiconductor structures).

Heterojunction catalyst	Electrode preparation	Electrolyte	HER overpotential	Refs.
Ag/TiO ₂ /RGO	drop-casting	0.1 M KOH	800 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[53]
Ni ₃ S ₂ -MoS ₂ @TiO ₂	hydrothermal + ALD	1.0 M KOH	49 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[54]
Ni ₃ S ₂ @TiO ₂	hydrothermal + ALD	1.0 M KOH	190 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[54]
Pt-TiO ₂ @MoS ₂	Hydrothermal	Na ₂ S/ Na ₂ SO ₃	400 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[55]
Au /MoS ₂ @TiO ₂	CVD	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	146 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[56]
MoS ₂ /TiO ₂	Hydrothermal	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	108 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[57]
MoS ₂ -BN@TiO ₂	Hydrothermal	0.25 M Na ₂ SO ₄	990 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[58]
MoS ₂ @TiO ₂	Thermal-oxidation and spraying	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	114 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[59]
MoP@Mo ₂ N	Thermal in nitrogen	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	89 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[60]
Ag ₂ S@CuS	Chemical dealloying	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	200 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	[61]
bTiO ₂ NTs@TaS ₂	Electrophoretic/activation	1 M PBS	81±4 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	this work
bTiO ₂ NTs@Au@TaS ₂	Electrophoretic/activation	1 M PBS	70±3 mV@10 mA cm ⁻²	this work

an additional energy input led to the further enhancement of HER performance. We also propose a mechanism explaining the high photo-electrode activity toward HER (considering better experimental results with the utilization of bTiO₂NTs@Au@TaS₂ hetero-electrode in photo-electrochemical mode – Figure 5E). The reduction of titanium oxide creates additional levels in its band gap, which facilitate light absorption at both short and long wavelengths (designated as λ_1 and λ_2) of the sunlight spectrum. In addition, the presence of Au nanostructures results in bTiO₂ band alignment and facilitates the excitation and migration of charge carriers too. In turn, the cracking of TaS₂ flakes creates additional edges and defects that act as redox-active sites. Plasmon assistance can result in the additional excitation of electrons in the structure of bTiO₂ from the ground state or from vacancies and defects (this process is designated as P₁ and P₂). Then the photo-excited electrons are transferred to redox-active TaS₂, while the Au nanostructures sandwiched between bTiO₂ and TaS₂ can promote the electron transfer (even in the dark). Due to the abundance of redox-active centers on cracked TaS₂, the extracted electrons can efficiently participate in proton reduction, leading to HER efficiency comparable to or better than that of the Pt standard. Since the experiments were performed in the photoelectrochemical regime, the residual holes are transferred to the counter electrode and consumed in the second water-splitting half-reaction (oxygen evolution).

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, the creation and utilization of a heterojunction photoelectrode comprising a coupled bTiO₂ nanotube array and self-activated 3R-TaS₂ flakes with (or without) the addition of plasmon-active intermediate Au nanostructures are proposed for efficient hydrogen production. In the proposed photo-electrode design, the partial reduction of TiO₂ to black titanium enhances light absorption, resulting in efficient photoexcitation of electrons and holes (the electrons then drain to TaS₂). The preliminary self-activation of TaS₂ (performed in a two-chamber cell separated by a proton exchange membrane) leads to flake(s) cracking which significantly improves semiconductor coupling and their catalytic activity. The addition of gold nanostructures between

bTiO₂ and TaS₂ promotes the charge transfer between bTiO₂ and TaS₂, enhances light absorption, and ensures plasmon triggering of catalytic activity in experiments performed in the photoelectrochemical regime as well. Created photo-electrode was employed for HER with a particular focus on the operation at high current densities and neutral pH. It was demonstrated that at current densities above 250 mA cm⁻² (and up to 500 mA cm⁻²) the catalytic activity of the proposed photo hetero-electrodes surpasses the efficiency of bulk platinum, especially in the case of Au intermediate nanostructures and the utilization of sunlight as an additional energy input. We also demonstrated the high stability of the proposed photo hetero-electrodes, even in the high current density hydrogen evolution. Generally, this study demonstrates the great attractiveness of the proposed heterojunction design for potential applications in green hydrogen production at a “close to industrial” scale without the utilization of traditional high-cost Pt or Pd.

4. Experimental Section

Description of the used materials, preparation of TaS₂ flakes and bTiO₂, creation of photo hetero-electrode as well as characterization techniques are described in detail in Supporting Information.

Briefly, 3R-TaS₂ was prepared in accordance with the previous work, by the sulfurization of tantalum oxide in the CS₂ vapor at elevated temperature.^[37] Porous bTiO₂ substrates were created by subsequent anodization/reduction of Ti foil. Deposition of the gold layer on bTiO₂ was performed by magnetron sputtering and followed by inert plasma treatment for the creation of plasmon-active Au nanostructures. The TaS₂ flakes were subsequently deposited on bTiO₂@Au (or simple bTiO₂) and electrochemically self-activated. Activation was performed in an H-type cell, with Nafion separation membrane.

Electrochemical measurements were performed in LSV or chronoamperometry mode in acidic (0.5 M H₂SO₄) or neutral (1 M phosphate buffer solution, pH 7.2) electrolyte. EmStat4s HR potentiostat (Palm Instruments, Netherlands) was used for measurement and electrode self-activation, performed at acidic pH. In all cases, Pt foil counter electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode were used. Electrochemical measurements were performed in the dark or under sample illumination with light emitting diode sources (Thorlabs), with the intensity on the sample surface equal to 25 mW cm⁻² or with the utilization of simulated sunlight (Solar Simulator SciSun-300, Class AAA, the intensity on the sample surface adjusted to 100 mW cm⁻²).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10786639>, reference number 10786640.

Keywords

black titania @ TMDCs, high current density, hydrogen evolution, neutral pH, plasmon

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